

THE BIOECOLOGICAL AND MEDICINAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PAEONIA L.

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Abstract

This article discusses the distribution range of *Paeonia* L. species, their adaptation to the environment, as well as ornamental and medicinal characteristics. Information is presented on the presence of accumulation of heavy metals in soils with different levels of pollution.

Key words: Peony, *Paeonia*, *Paeonia lactiflora*, root, heavy metal, microorganism, soil, greenhouse effect.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассмотрены ареал видов *Paeonia* L., их адаптация к окружающей среде, а также декоративные и лечебные свойства. Представлены сведения о наличии накопления тяжелых металлов в почвах с разным уровнем загрязнения.

Ключевые слова: Пеонь, *Paeonia*, *Paeonia lactiflora*, корень, тяжелый металл, микроорганизмы, почва, парниковый эффект.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada *Paeonia* L. turlarining areali, atrof-muhitga adaptiv moslashishi, manzaralilik va dorivorlik xususiyatlari yoritilgan. Turli darajada ifloslangan tuproqlarda mavjud og'ir metallarni akkumilyatsiyasi xususiyatining mavjudligi kabi ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Peony, *Paeonia*, *Paeonia lactiflora*, ildiz, og'ir metall, mikroorganizmlar, tuproq, issiqxona effekti.

The genus of *Paeonia* L. is widely known for its large flowers and colorful colors, rich in aroma. In addition to its important ornamental value, peony also has important medicinal and economic value.

Paeonia plants are distributed around the world. China has rich peony germplasm resources and is considered the center of distribution of peony [1]. Peony has been cultivated in China for over 1600 years [2].

There are only two wild peonies in Uzbekistan, respectively *P. hybrida* and *P. albiflora*, peony germplasm resources are scarce. Peony can be widely used in garden landscapes due to its

high ornamental value, tolerance, and wide adaptability to the environment [3]. In the future, we will try to introduce *Paeonia* plants from China to contribute to the popularization of this valuable plant in Uzbekistan.

Planting peony also has a useful impact on the environment. In the ecological field, heavy metals are generally considered to be pollutants in the soil, but peony can absorb these heavy metal elements. And the types and concentrations of heavy metal elements contained in different organs are different [4]. The roots of *Paeonia* plants contain paeonol and paeoniflorin, which are bioactive substances that can be used to treat diseases such as breast cancer and neuropathic pain. The organic matter, pH value, and heavy metal elements Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} content in the soil all promote the accumulation of these bioactive substances [5].

By observing the peony root ring also can judge the past climate change [6]. There is a strong correlation between the main ecological factors such as soil humus, annual average temperature, altitude, and the bioactivities of peony roots [7]. Studies have confirmed that the roots of *Paeonia lactiflora* can also absorb heavy metal elements Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Fe^{2+} in the soil [8].

The root microbial community of peony is affected by soil pH and alkaline phosphatase [9]. Therefore, peonies are suitable for growing in neutral or slightly alkaline soils with loose soil, breathability, and good drainage. It can also use microorganisms in the soil to maintain the characteristics and functions required by the environment [10]. The microbial resources in the roots of peony also can be used for bioremediation, organic matter degradation and disease resistance [11].

As the global climate warms, a series of environmental problems will arise. For example, glacier melting causes sea level rise, decreased biological diversity, drought stress, etc. The greenhouse effect also has an important impact on the growth of peony.

The long germination period and low germination rate of peony seeds are the main reasons for its low reproduction rate. The winter temperature in tropical and subtropical southern regions is relatively high, which to some extent affects the release of herbaceous peony bud dormancy and flowering [12]. Drought stress can also affect the flowering size and length of tree peony [13]. Therefore, how peonies adapt to the ecological environment is also a question worth studying.

Peony, as a high-end cut flower plant, has important significance in urban greening and landscaping construction. In the botanical garden of the National University of Uzbekistan, we have now planted two species of peony, namely *P. lactiflora* and *P. officinalis*. In the future, we will continue to conduct in-depth research on the morphological, ecological, physiological, anatomical and other characteristics of these plants, providing theoretical basis for their development and popularization in Uzbekistan.

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